

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**A STUDY OF FREQUENCY AND SEVERITY
OF DEPRESSION IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETES
MELLITUS IN A TERTIARY CARE SETTING**Dr. Abdullah Bin Sana ullah¹, Dr. Faisal Iqbal², Dr. Reema Aijaz¹¹Jinnah Hospital Lahore,²Medical Officer at District Headquarter Hospital Kasur.**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: This research is objected to explore about current practices of inclusive education in Pakistan. In every society medical students are soundless but noticeable participants. In accordance with country policies and implementations, medical students face many barriers to getting education. It is having much importance to craft such study environment that meets the requirements of medical students also.

Methodology: A descriptive investigation design was employed for this education in order to investigate regular medical teacher knowledge concerning inclusive medical education practices in the medical college in Lahore setting. Data from the participants was gathered in one point in time. The selected population for this study is government medical college of Lahore, Punjab. The population of medical college from respected area has been drawn from data of University of Health Sciences Lahore. From University of Health Sciences Lahore data bank total population of medical colleges 6 medical college. By applying simple random sampling, 10 samples of 10 medical teachers in each sample has been taken. The sample size for this study has been objected as 100 medical teachers out of total population.

Results: SPSS regression analysis of 100 recorded responses have been run and the results of test showed that there is 90 percent change effect of independent variable on dependent variable. The significance level has been reported as .000 highly significant of study variables in this study. In regression analysis 't' value is significantly higher than 2 with F value 292.82 showing the results of model fit. This association of independent variable 'medical teacher's knowledge' and dependent variable 'Inclusive medical education' representing by recorded responses are highly associated in Pakistani perspective of this study.

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Please cite this article in press Abdullah Bin Sana ullah et al., *A study of frequency and severity Of depression in patients With Diabetes Mellitus In A Tertiary Care Setting.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(06).

INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes is one of the leading public health concerns of the 21st century, the prevalence in the world is more than 8.5% [10]. Worldwide current estimate of about 415 million. It is expected that the number of people will increase by 2030 by two-thirds to 552 million people (Whitting DR, et. al.). It corresponds 1 in 11 chance of developing diabetes in life, with one death each Six seconds after this condition. Despite these high rates, it is still a third of people with diabetes go unnoticed (Wang X, et. al.). Diabetes is also a costly disease of global importance. Expenditures amount to more than 670 billion dollars, which is approximately 12% of global health spending. It is expected that by 2040, these costs will increase by 20% and exceed \$ 800 billion in USA (IDF, 2015). A rapid increase in the incidence of diabetes worldwide is associated primarily with an increase in caloric intake. The low physical activity associated with the spread of the Western lifestyle is associated with simultaneous increase in prevalence of overweight and obesity among developed and developed Countries (Ozougwu O et. Al.). However, the causes of diabetes are complex and include a wide range of established Risk factors including obesity, smoking, genetics, physical inactivity and nutrition Behaviors (Chen L, et. Al.). Due to the serious and persistent nature of health risks, diabetes is a disease that is needed a high level of professional support, usually through multidisciplinary medical teams; include general practitioners, diabetes counselors, nurses, endocrinologists and others. It is beyond that it is a disease that requires a high degree of alertness and self-control of the patients.

South-East Asia had 59 million affected individuals, With 1 out of every 10 Pakistanis being affected from the disease[3]. The reported prevalence of depression in patients with diabetes mellitus varies from 8 to 27% (Bach JF, et. Al.). Among the individuals suffering from Diabetes in Karachi 43.5% were found have depression (McCullough DK, et. Al.). Another matched case-control study conducted at civil Hospital Karachi on 592 patients of whom 296 were diagnosed Diabetics showed percentages as high as 60% (of whom 103 suffered from moderate to severe depression while 73

suffered from mild depression). However, still there are reports that show other end of the spectrum with only 14.7% (189) of the studied population of 1290 having depression (Stene LC, et. al.). Depression in these patients leads to poor glycemic control due to lower compliance to medications and self-care activities which as a result would lead to more complicated course of diabetes. If diabetics can be diagnosed and treated timely for depression, treating them for depression can make them more compliant to management of diabetes. Which will lead to increased quality of life of these individuals (Whitting DR, et. al.).

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

Determination of depression frequency in patients with diabetes mellitus attending Diabetic clinic at Jinnah Hospital Lahore. To find out frequency and severity of depression in patients with diabetes mellitus in Lahore District. To compare the symptoms of depression among Diabetic patients and population in general. To find out the risk factors for depression among diabetic patients in district Lahore.

Operational Definitions

•Diabetes mellitus: Individuals taking Oral hypoglycemic or subcutaneous Insulin for more than 3 months as determined by history.

METHODOLOGY:

Total 250 cases of Diabetes mellitus fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria were included in this study. Beck Depressive inventory – II questionnaire of each patient in this study was answered by the patient in the presence of physician in endocrinology outdoor of Jinnah Hospital Lahore. Performa with all fields was recorded by the same physician.

RESULTS:**AGE DISTRIBUTION**

Between June 2017 and December 2017, 250 patients visiting attending diabetic clinic at Jinnah Hospital Lahore Patients with age ranging 18 years to 60 years with mean of 42.82 and standard deviation of 11.65. Histogram below shows this pattern as majority of the patients were within 30 years to 60 years of age.

	Descriptive Statistics				
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	250	18	60	42.82	11.653
Marital Status	250	0	2	.89	.671
Income/Month (Rs./month)	250	1	4	1.93	.808
Smoking Status	250	0	2	.45	.722

Frequency and Severity of Depression

According to the Table below 54% of the diabetics were diagnosed to have depression of some severity with majority of the population among the depressed lying between mild clinical depression and moderate depression i.e. 20.4% and 22% of the total 250 patients respectively.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistic

Beck Depressive Inventory – II (BDI-II) Score	Frequency	Percent
Normal (BDI - II score Less Than 17)	115	46.0
Mild clinical depression (BDI- II score: 17 – 20)	51	20.4
Moderate depression (BDI- II score: 21 – 30)	55	22.0
Severe depression (BDI- II score: 31 – 40)	29	11.6
Total	250	100.0

Table 3. Frequency and Severity of Depression

Relationship of incidence of depression with Duration of Diabetes

Table below shows that Prevalence of depression among the different age groups. It's worthwhile to note that that in duration group of less than 6 month depression was only in 3% of diabetics and increases to 9.6% in 6 months to 2 years duration group. Then its incidence suddenly increases to 40.7 % in 2 years to 5 years duration group and then stays almost steady at 32.6% in 6 years to 10 years group before falling down to 14.1% in greater than 10 years duration group. This has p-value of less than 0.01. Concluding that prevalence of depression in diabetes is minimal at the diagnosis of the diabetes mellitus but grows with increased duration of disease before falling in the group whose duration of diabetes mellitus is greater than 10 years.

Depression status * Duration Of Diabetes Mellitus Crosstabulation

Count

		Duration Of Diabetes Mellitus					Total
		Less Than 6 Months	6 Months - 2 Years	2 Years - 5 Years	6 Years - 10 Years	Greater Than 10 Years	
Depression status	Normal	17	24	47	14	13	115
	Depressed	4	13	55	44	19	135
Total		21	37	102	58	32	250

Depression status * Duration Of Diabetes Mellitus Crosstabulation

Table 4. Relationship of incidence of depression with Duration of Diabetes (P-value less than 0.5)

Relationship of HbA1C level with Depression

Table below shows the relationship between the glycemic control of the patient to the depression. It is observed that 37.5% of patients in extreme depression belonged to HbA1c range of 6.5 mg/dl – 7.4 mg/dl suffered from extreme form of depression. Also 31.3% of the patients in extreme depression belonged in the HbA1c range of 9.5 mg/dl – 10.4 mg/dl. 33.3% of the patients suffering from Mild clinical depression had their HbA1C within range of 7.5mg/dl – 8.4mg/dl. These finding were not expected in lower glycemic range, but were considered nonsignificant because of nonsignificant p-value of 0.651. It is noted that depression was more prevalent among the individuals who had a better glycemic control i.e. HbA1c Less than 6.5 mg/dl had 7.4%, HbA1c 6.5 mg/dl - 7.4 mg/dl had 23%, HbA1c 7.5 mg/dl - 8.4 mg/dl had 25.2%, HbA1c 8.5 mg/dl - 9.4 mg/dl had 16.3%, HbA1c 9.5 mg/dl - 10.4 mg/dl had 14.8% and HbA1c greater than 10.5 mg/dl 7.4% had 13.3% prevalence of depression among the study population with the p-value of 0.948, and was considered insignificant.

Table 4. Frequency of depression with relation to HBA1C level.(P-Value = 0.948)**Depression status * HbA1c Range Crosstabulation**

Count		HbA1c Range						Total
		HbA1c Less than 6.5 mg/dl	HbA1c 6.5 mg/dl - 7.4 mg/dl	HbA1c 7.5 mg/dl - 8.4 mg/dl	HbA1c 8.5 mg/dl - 9.4 mg/dl	HbA1c 9.5 mg/dl - 10.4 mg/dl	HbA1c greater than 10.5 mg/dl	
Depression status	Normal	11	22	28	22	18	14	115
	Depressed	10	31	34	22	20	18	135
Total		21	53	62	44	38	32	250

DISCUSSION:

Diabetes Mellitus is a syndrome, in which chronic hyperglycemia leads to various metabolic disorders due to relative deficiency or resistance of insulin. A Group of metabolic disorders that share a common characteristic feature of Hyperglycemia is referred to as Diabetes mellitus (DM). How various genetics and environmental factors interact with each other determines what kind of clinical subset of this syndrome may prevail. Some of the common physiological pathways followed by these subsets of diabetes mellitus comprise decreased glucose utilization, insulin secretion, and increased glucose production.

3000 Years ago ancient Egyptians described a clinical syndrome that has many similarities with the modern day description of diabetes mellitus. However for the term "Diabetes" was used for the first time by Aretus of Cappodocia (81-133AD). Later, by Thomas Willis in 1675 the word "mellitus" (honey sweet) was added when sweetness of urine and blood was discovered. 1776 was the year when Dobson confirmed that excessive sugar in urine and blood due to its sweets. In modern time, the role of the liver in glycogenesis was described by Claude Bernard in 1857. However it took 3 more decades till the role of the pancreas in pathogenesis of diabetes was discovered by Mering and Minkowski in 1889. Later, in 1921 insulin was isolated and used in clinics by Banting and Best for first time.

Incidence of Diabetes Mellitus is on the rise, Global Prevalence of Diabetes Mellitus was 285 million in 2010 with estimated that 25.8 million affected people in America. The prevalence is similar in men and women throughout most age ranges. South-East Asia had 59 million affected individuals, With 1 out of every 10 Pakistanis being affected from the disease.

CLASSIFICATION:

Diabetes can be categorized into various types based upon their etiological factor:

1. Diabetes Mellitus Type I: Primarily beta cell destruction leads to absolute insulin deficiency leading hyperglycemia.
2. Diabetes Mellitus Type II: Two end of the spectrum include
 - a. May present in initial phase with predominantly insulin resistance causing relative insulin deficiency.
 - b. Which might later evolve to a state with predominant insulin secretory defect along with insulin resistance
3. Genetic Defects causing pancreatic Beta cell dysfunction include:
 - i. MODY 1 : Hepatocellular nuclear transcription factor 4
 - ii. MODY 2 : Related to Glucokinase
 - iii. MODY 3 : Hepatocellular nuclear transcription factor – 1
 - iv. MODY 4 : Insulin promoter factor – 1
 - v. MODY 5 : Hepatocyte nuclear transcription factor – 1
 - vi. MODY 6 : NeuroD1
 - vii. Miscellaneous : Mitochondrial DNA, Subunits of ATP-sensitive potassium channel Proinsulin or insulin
4. Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM)

DIABETES MELLITUS TYPE – I

It is characterized by destruction of the pancreatic beta cells which causes absolute insulin deficiency. It comprises 5 to 10 percent of the DM patients. Genome-wide association studies has shown no overlap between that type 1 and type 2 diabetes, although inflammation (e.g., interleukin-1 mediated) is involved in destruction of beta cells in islet of Langerhans[4]. When these genetically vulnerable patients trigger these genes by one or more environmental mediators (hygiene hypothesis: improved sanitation leaves immune system idle causing increased autoimmune disorders) [5]. The process takes several months or years during which

the subject is asymptomatic and euglycemic before developing overt DM[6]. It is known that many genes affect the risk of type 1 DM (HLA-Dqalpha; HLA-Dqbeta; HLA-DR, PR proinsulin, the PTPN22 gene, and CTLA-4). HLA alleles play major role while major histocompatibility complex (MHC) just have a minimal influence on the risk of developing DM type 1[7]. A cohort study exhibited main direct association between birth weight and risk of type 1 diabetes[8]. Also Cow's milk has been bound to be culprit of triggering these genes shown in one Finland study[68]. Whatever the trigger or gene may be involved but one thing is noted that that proinsulin/ Insulin itself is the likely primary target for the auto antibodies [69]. Chronic hepatitis C virus infection, Coxsackie and enteroviruses have also been found culprit in destroying the islet cells in pancreas[70].

DIABETES MELLITUS TYPE – 2

Insulin resistance in DM leads to hyperglycemia which in turn causes impairment of pancreatic beta cells thus the vicious cycle of downward spiral of increased insulin resistance and decreased insulin continues leading to complications of DM. This metabolic syndrome is a cocktail of raised low-density-lipoprotein (LDL), decreased serum high-density-lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol concentrations which leads to numerous cardiovascular complications.

Gestational Diabetes Mellitus:

Diabetogenic hormones such as growth hormone, placental lactogen, corticotropin releasing hormone (CRH), and progesterone along with other factors such as maternal fat deposition, decreased exercise, and increased food intake causes insulin resistance in pregnant women whose pancreatic function is not adequate to supply additional requirements of insulin that body demands during gestational period. These patients can go as far as developing overt DM.

SCREENING:

Diabetes Mellitus type 2

Data over screening is controversial where,

- American Diabetes Association (ADA) recommends Screening for DM 2 only. The susceptible individuals are overweight (BMI greater than 25, waist circumference greater than 38 inch) with positive family history in the first degree relative. Others who are at risk such as people with physical inactivity, history of gestational diabetes, hypertension or dyslipidemia should also be screened.

- While United States Preventive Services Task Force (USPTF) differed on the screening of non-pregnant women and was against such a practice, it only recommends screening in individuals with hypertension (blood pressure >135/80 mmHg).

- Still Canadian Task Force wants only patients with hypertension and dyslipidemia to be screened.

- Tests used for this purpose are:

- Fasting plasma glucose (FPG)
- Glycated hemoglobin (A1C) for those who didn't fast over night
- 2-h 75 g OGTT

DIAGNOSIS:

Random blood glucose value of ≥ 200 mg/dl along with classical symptoms of hyperglycemia (polyuria, weight loss, blurry vision and thirst) establishes the diagnosis of DM. However the long-term goal in diabetes is to prevent its complications (this has been related to the development of retinopathy whose prevalence in noted to increase with FPG ≥ 126 mg/dl), 2hr-OGTT ≥ 200 mg/dl and A1C $\geq 6.5\%$. So various bodies enlisted below have devised their own respective criterion.

Numerous high-quality epidemiological studies and meta-analyses have shown that depression in diabetics occurs about twice as often as expected, with estimates ranging from 11% to 47% in some studies. In order to investigate the possible causal and etiological connections between depression and diabetes, numerous longitudinal studies were also carried out. These studies show the bi-directional nature of this relationship, most of which report stronger diabetes-predictive effects, as for feedback (for example, OR = 1.60 versus OR = 1.15).

Prediabetes is a disease characterized by hyperglycemia that is slightly below the threshold for diabetes (ie, from 5.6 to 7.0 mmol / l); Most people with prediabetes develop diabetes without intervention, and conversion rates can reach 70% [30]. It has been found that depression more than doubles the patient's prediabetes risk of diabetes within 4.5 years (OS = 10.65 versus 4.14). The combined effects of depression and prediabetes are synergistic, with diabetes risk. Although no link between depression and diabetes has been found in several individual studies, numerous meta-analyses of longitudinal studies on this topic are currently underway, all of which yielded significant combined risk assessments (from RR =) from 1.17 to OP = 1, 60).

CONCLUSION:

Depression is moderately associated with the onset of diabetes, and these effects become more serious as the disease progresses. In our study depression is seen 54.4% of the diabetics. Majority of diabetics suffered from mild to moderate depression. Based on this prevalence, we can recommend that every diabetic should be screened for depression at least once while being managed for diabetes mellitus.

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